

Detecting Fraudulent Credit Card Transactions using Ensemble Methods

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ABSTRACT – Detecting fraudulent credit card transactions is a significant challenge for financial institutions, as cybercriminals often impersonate legitimate users to conduct unauthorized transactions. Since every approved transaction requires verification, effective fraud detection mechanisms are essential. Ensemble learning techniques can enhance fraud detection by analyzing both synthetic and real-world consumer transaction datasets. Models such as XGBoost, random forests, and naive Bayes classifiers are tested, with performance evaluated based on accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. Results show that ensemble classifiers perform well on real transaction data but struggle with synthetic datasets. Real-world transaction systems adapt quickly to structured patterns, improving fraud detection effectiveness. However, the deterministic nature of these systems, combined with minimal randomness, may increase the vulnerability of credit card information.

Index Terms – Fintech, credit card fraud detection, ensemble learning, machine learning, simulated data set, real-world data set.

I. INTRODUCTION

Identifying credit card fraud is vital to preventing unauthorized transactions and financial damage. In 2020, reported fraud cases surpassed 393,000, leading to losses of \$28.6 billion, a 19.3% rise from 2017. Experts estimate that these losses could climb to \$408 billion within the next decade. Fraud detection relies on various methods, including statistical techniques like outlier detection and machine learning models such as decision trees, support vector machines, and neural networks. To enhance accuracy, ensemble learning approaches like bagging, boosting (AdaBoost, XGBoost), and stacking are commonly employed. It examines the performance of Naïve Bayes, bagging, and boosting classifiers using real and

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synthetic datasets to identify the most effective fraud detection approach while providing recommendations for future advancements. Based, on a data set of credit card transactions of European Union consumers available in the Kaggle repository and the synthetic Sparkov dataset. An attempt to find the best ensemble-based model for solving the credit card detection problem is made in this work.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Credit card fraud detection is a crucial financial security concern, requiring efficient and accurate models to distinguish between fraudulent and legitimate transactions. Ensemble methods, which combine multiple classifiers, have emerged as powerful techniques to enhance fraud detection accuracy. Early fraud detection models relied on supervised learning algorithms such as Decision Trees, Logistic Regression, and Support Vector Machines (SVM). However, these models often suffer from data imbalance issues, where fraudulent transactions are significantly fewer than legitimate ones. Chan et al. (1999) proposed an undersampling technique to handle imbalanced data in fraud detection, while Dal Pozzolo et al. (2015) used cost-sensitive learning to mitigate class imbalance in fraud detection.

Ensemble methods improve detection rates by leveraging multiple base models, including bagging, boosting, and stacking. Random Forest (Breiman, 2001), a bagging-based method, builds multiple decision trees and aggregates predictions, performing well in fraud detection due to its robustness against overfitting. XGBoost (Chen & Guestrin, 2016), an advanced boosting algorithm, is known for its high accuracy in fraud detection by reducing bias and variance. Recently we had focuses on hybrid models that integrate multiple ensemble techniques. Bhattacharyya et al. (2011) developed a hybrid approach combining decision trees with boosting to enhance fraud detection performance. Carcillo et al. (2018) introduced a deep learning-ensemble hybrid model, outperforming traditional machine learning methods. To assess model effectiveness, evaluation metrics such as Precision & Recall, F1-Score, and AUC-ROC are commonly used. Precision and Recall measure accuracy in detecting fraudulent cases, F1 -Score balances precision and recall for imbalanced datasets, and AUC-ROC evaluates model performance across different thresholds. Ensemble methods have demonstrated significant improvements in fraud detection accuracy and robustness. Future we should explore deep learning-based ensembles, real-time detection frameworks, and adversarial learning techniques to enhance fraud detection capabilities.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology follows a systematic approach to detecting fraudulent credit card transactions using machine learning and ensemble methods. The process begins with the selection of two datasets: the European customers dataset and the Sparkov synthetic dataset. These datasets are subjected to data preprocessing and cleaning to remove inconsistencies, handle missing values, and ensure data quality. Since fraudulent transactions are significantly fewer than legitimate ones, class imbalance is a major challenge in fraud detection. To address this, three dataset handling strategies are applied: Oversampling, which increases the number of fraudulent transactions by duplicating minority class instances; Undersampling, which reduces the number of legitimate transactions to balance both classes; and Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE), which generates synthetic fraudulent transaction samples to improve class representation. These preprocessing strategies are separately applied to both datasets, resulting in six variations: European customers dataset with oversampling, undersampling, and SMOTE, as well as Sparkov synthetic dataset with

the same three variations.

Fig 1: System Architecture

After preprocessing, classification is performed using three machine learning algorithms: **Naïve Bayes**, a probabilistic classifier based on Bayes' theorem; **Random Forest**, an ensemble learning method that constructs multiple decision trees and aggregates their results; and **Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)**, a powerful boosting algorithm that enhances model accuracy through iterative learning. These classifiers are trained and tested on the processed datasets to assess their fraud detection performance.

Fig 2: Applying Undersampling Strategy

To evaluate the effectiveness of the models, multiple performance metrics are utilized. F1 Score is used to balance precision and recall, ensuring that both false positives and false negatives are minimized. Accuracy measures the overall correctness of predictions. Validation techniques are applied to assess the generalizability of the models, preventing overfitting. Precision is specifically considered to ensure that the identified fraudulent transactions are truly fraudulent, reducing false alarms. Enhances model accuracy through iterative learning.

Fig 3: Density probability distributions of F1 score of dataset and model

By systematically applying different dataset balancing techniques, machine learning classifiers, and evaluation metrics, this approach ensures a comprehensive assessment of fraud detection performance, leading to insights into the most effective methods for improving security in financial transactions.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The performance of fraudulent transaction detection is evaluated using Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost). Among these, XGBoost performs the best due to its ability to handle imbalanced datasets effectively. It optimizes decision boundaries through gradient boosting, reducing false negatives while maintaining high precision. This ensures better detection of fraudulent transactions compared to other models.

Fig 4: UI of detecting Credit card frauds

Naïve Bayes, being a probabilistic classifier, struggles with imbalanced data, leading to a higher false negative rate. It assumes feature independence, which does not always hold in financial transactions, affecting its accuracy. Unlike XGBoost and Random Forest, it fails to capture complex fraud patterns. Overall, XGBoost

combined with SMOTE provides the best fraud detection results with the highest F1 Score and precision. Random Forest also performs well by leveraging multiple decision trees to classify transactions accurately. It reduces overfitting by averaging predictions from different trees, leading to stable performance. While it achieves high precision, it sometimes misclassifies fraudulent transactions due to class imbalance. However, applying SMOTE improves its recall, making it more effective in fraud detection.

Fig 5: Registration UI

Fig 6: Accuracy pie chart representation

XGBoost's superior performance is attributed to its iterative boosting process, which continuously refines weak classifiers to improve overall prediction accuracy. By assigning higher weights to misclassified fraudulent transactions, it effectively reduces false negatives while maintaining a low false positive rate. This makes it highly reliable for fraud detection, as it adapts to complex transaction patterns and learns from data imbalances. The combination of XGBoost with SMOTE further enhances its ability to detect fraudulent

transactions, making it the most effective model among those evaluated

Fig 7: Line graph representation for accuracy

Detection Of Credit Card Transaction Type III

ENTER ALL DATASETS DETAILS HERE !!!

Enter FId	<input type="text"/>	Enter Trans_Data	<input type="text"/>
Enter CC_No	<input type="text"/>	Enter CC_type	<input type="text"/>
Enter Trans_Type	<input type="text"/>	Enter Amount	<input type="text"/>
Enter Firstname	<input type="text"/>	Enter Lastname	<input type="text"/>
Enter Gender	<input type="text"/>	Enter Age	<input type="text"/>
Enter lat	<input type="text"/>	Enter lon	<input type="text"/>
Enter Threshold	<input type="text"/>		

Detection Of Credit Card Transaction Type : ----Fraudulent Not Found----

Fig 8: Prediction of Results

V. CONCLUSION

The detection of fraudulent credit card transactions is significantly improved using ensemble machine learning methods, with XGBoost emerging as the most effective classifier. Its ability to handle imbalanced datasets, optimize decision boundaries, and reduce false negatives makes it highly reliable for fraud detection. When combined with SMOTE, XGBoost further enhances recall and precision, ensuring a balanced and accurate classification of fraudulent transactions. Random Forest also demonstrates strong performance by leveraging multiple decision trees to improve fraud detection accuracy. While it benefits from SMOTE, it is slightly less effective than XGBoost in handling complex fraud patterns. Naïve Bayes, on the other hand, struggles with imbalanced data and fails to detect fraudulent transactions effectively, making it the least suitable model for this task. The findings highlight the importance of selecting the right combination of

machine learning models and data balancing techniques for fraud detection. Implementing XGBoost with SMOTE provides a robust approach to identifying fraudulent transactions while minimizing false positives and false negatives. Future work can explore deep learning-based models and real-time detection systems to further enhance fraud prevention in financial transactions.

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